

The Role of Membrane Features on the Permeability Behavior of Polymersomes and the Potential Impacts on Drug Encapsulation and Release

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT

Self-assembled bilayer structures such as those produced from amphiphilic block copolymers (polymersomes) are potentially useful in a wide array of applications including the production of artificial cells and organelles, nanoreactors and delivery systems. These constructs are of important fundamental interest, and they are also frequently considered towards advances in bionanotechnology and nanomedicine. In this framework, membrane permeability is perhaps the most important property of such functional materials. Having in mind these considerations, we herein report the manufacturing of intrinsically permeable polymersomes produced using block copolymers comprising poly[2-(diisopropylamino)-ethyl methacrylate] (PDPA) as the hydrophobic segment. Although being water insoluble at pH 7.4, its $pK_{a(\text{PDPA})} \sim 6.8$ leads to the presence of a fraction of protonated amino groups close to the physiological pH, thus conducting to the formation of relatively swollen hydrophobic segments. Rhodamine B-loaded vesicles demonstrated that this feature confers inherent permeability to the polymeric membrane which can still be modulated to some extent by the solution pH. Indeed, even at higher pH values where the PDPA chains are fully deprotonated, the experiments demonstrate that the membranes remain permeable. While membrane permeability can be for instance regulated by introducing membrane proteins and DNA nanopores, examples of membrane-forming polymers with intrinsic permeability have been seldom reported so far, and the possibility to regulate flow of chemicals in these compartments by tuning block copolymer features and ambient conditions is of due relevance. The permeable nature of PDPA membranes possibly applies to a wide array of small molecules and these findings can in principle be translocated to a variety of disparate bio-related applications.

INTRODUCTION

Molecular self-assembly is a prevalent process in nature to form patterns (formation of DNA double-helix, folding of polypeptides, phospholipids arrangement in cell membranes, to name a few) required for the existence of living systems.¹ Mimicking such phenomenon inspired in biology (the autonomous organization of components) by using artificial molecular building blocks *via* a bottom-up process has long been of particular interest aiming to create functional materials that use the same principle.²⁻⁴ Particularly, the self-assembly of amphiphilic block copolymers in aqueous milieu can be finely controlled by the hydrophilic-to-hydrophobic ratio. This is thermodynamically governed by the packing parameter (p) which is the ratio between the molecular volume of the insoluble chains and the volume effectively occupied by the chains in the self-assembly. Typically, spherical micelles are produced when $p \leq 1/3$, cylindrical micelles are formed at $1/3 < p \leq 1/2$ and vesicles (commonly referred to as polymersomes) when $1/2 < p \leq 1$.^{5,6} Due to similarities with cellular membranes and viral capsids, the polymersomes regularly receive greater attention. These structures embrace an aqueous inner compartment surrounded by a polymeric membrane and, thanks to the compartmentalization feature, such arrangement has led to outstanding developments in mimicking cell-like organelles.⁷⁻⁹

Since the engineering of such type of assembly potentialize the incorporation of hydrophilic molecules and macromolecules within the lumen, they are also promising platforms for nanobiocatalysis and therapeutic applications.¹⁰⁻¹⁵ The confinement of reaction spaces usually provides enhanced stability to catalytic compounds (such as enzymes)¹⁶ as well as protection from premature degradation of active agents (such as drugs) during navigation in the bloodstream.¹⁷ Nevertheless, for the large majority of intended applications, the compartmentalized environment must also enable the incoming

and outgoing of compounds across the wall. As for biocatalytic applications, the polymeric membranes are required to exhibit selective permeability to allow the flow of substrates and products while retaining enzymes in the aqueous lumen.¹² Similarly, in the manufacturing of drug delivery systems, the membrane is supposed to ideally protect the therapeutic agent from degradation while navigating in healthy tissues nevertheless, release of the active agent at a target location is needed at a certain time.¹⁰ The flow regulation in these compartments essentially depends on the features of the polymeric membrane as well as on the transport mechanism. Truly, membrane permeability is possibly the most important property governing the potential application of polymersomes and therefore, the ability to tune and control such property is of due relevance.¹⁸⁻²¹ Compared to liposomes produced from smaller building units (lipids), due to the higher molecular weight constituents, polymersomes possess notably enhanced microstructural stability but, on the other hand, it typically endows poor bilayer permeability and the effective flow of materials is restricted by the hydrophobicity of the, normally thick, bilayer membranes.²² This feature can however be bypassed by using different strategies to obtain permeable polymersomes such as the incorporation of membrane proteins²³ and DNA nanopores,²⁴ thus making nano channels towards size-dependent permeability. On the other hand, the manufacturing of permeable and semipermeable polymeric membranes without the aid of external agents has been seldom evidenced. This is an outstanding advantage avoiding multistep and post-assembly procedures to produce pores to impart permeability. Amongst the few number of intrinsically permeable polymer vesicles, the ones composed by polystyrene-*b*-poly(isocyanalanine(2-thiophen-3-yl-ethyl)amide) (PS-*b*-PIAT) were proven to be inherently porous due to poor polymer packing.²⁵ Accordingly, biomacromolecules (enzymes) could be accommodated in the aqueous lumen and small molecules (substrates

and products) could diffuse in and out through the polymeric walls. Vesicles containing polyelectrolyte complexes in the wall (PICsomes) was also evidenced to be permeable to hydrophilic molecules.²⁶ Poly(ethylene glycol)-*b*-poly(2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate) polymersomes were also evidenced to be intrinsically permeable due to the hydrated nature of the only moderated hydrophobic poly(2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate) membrane-forming block.²⁷ Similar feature has been shown by manufacturing polymer vesicles using maltotriose and poly(*n*-propyloxazoline) exhibiting LCST-like behavior.²⁸ Intrinsic ion-permeable polymersomes based on β -cyclodextrin-cored star copolymers has been also reported²⁹ as well as proton permeable “breathing” vesicles.³⁰

In this framework, the use of stimuli-responsive swelled membranes as triggered upon external stimulus can provide selective membrane permeability.³¹ This can in principle be achieved by using stimuli-responsive polymers which uses external signals to mediate the permeability of the membranes, thus permitting tailor-made regulation of flow.³² Along these lines, poly[2-(diisopropylamino) ethyl methacrylate] (PDPA) is pH-switchable with $pK_a \sim 6.8$.³³ The pK_a value is relatively close to the physiological pH (pH 7.4) and therefore, it can in principle sense minimal changes in a biologically relevant pH region. Accordingly, structural changes in the polymeric walls can modify and regulate the flow of drugs and other chemicals. Taking into account the abovementioned considerations, this investigation relies on the permeability behavior of a variety of polymersomes produced using different amphiphilic block copolymers. Thanks to the recent advances in controlled polymerization processes, a wide array of macromolecules with manageable chemical nature and composition allowed for the engineering of complex vesicles with regulation over membrane thickness and permeability. Such investigation is supposed to be highly relevant since the permeability to small molecules

would accordingly make these entities suitable in a wide array of applications ranging from nanoreactors to cell mimicry, and therapeutic applications.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Chemicals

The block copolymers poly(2-methyl-2-oxazoline)_m-*b*-poly[2-(diisopropylamino)-ethyl methacrylate]_n were synthesized as previously described using a stepwise combination of cationic ring-opening (CROP) and reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) polymerization techniques.³⁴ The synthesis of the block copolymer PHPMA₂₉-*b*-PDPA₇₄ was performed by RAFT polymerization using a synthetic strategy previously described.¹⁷ Poly[*N*-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide]-*b*-poly[*N*-(4-isopropylphenylacetamide)ethyl methacrylate] herein named as PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈ was synthesized using similar synthetic approaches and different monomeric units.³⁵ The solvents methanol (anhydrous, 99.8%), chloroform (anhydrous, ≥ 99%) and tetrahydrofuran (anhydrous, ≥ 99.9%), Dulbecco's phosphate buffered saline (PBS), Rhodamine B (RhB), Sephadex[®] G-50 and the dialysis bag Spectra-Por[®] Float-A-Lyzer[®] G2 with MWCO 3.5-5 kDa were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The water used in the sample preparation was pretreated with a Milli-Q[®] Plus System (Millipore Corporation).

Preparation of the RhB-Loaded Liposomes

RhB-loaded liposomes were prepared by the lipid film hydration followed by extrusion. Ten-mg of hydrogenated soy phosphatidylcholine (HSPC, Avanti Polar lipids), 3.1 mg of 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphoethanolamine-*N*-[methoxy(polyethylene glycol)-2000] (ammonium salt) (18:0 PEG2000 PE; Avanti Polar lipids) and 3.2 mg of

cholesterol (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) were dissolved in 1 mL of chloroform/methanol mixture 9:1 (v/v). The solvent was afterwards completely removed by rotavapor forming a homogenous lipid film. The film was then hydrated using 4 mL of RhB solution in PBS (1.0 mg.mL⁻¹) and sonicated for 10 min. Then, five freeze-thaw cycles were performed to reduce the lamellarity of the produced liposomes and increase the encapsulation of the dye. Finally, the solution was filtered with 1 µm and 0.45 µm Whatman filters and extruded at 60 C° twenty times using Avanti mini-extruder with a 200 nm polycarbonate membrane filter. The free RhB dye was removed by passing the liposomes in G50 column with PBS.

Preparation of the RhB-Loaded Polymersomes: The polymersomes were produced using the solvent-switch method. Sixteen-mg of the polymer samples were dissolved in 1 mL of THF/methanol (60/40 v/v). Subsequently, RhB 1.0 mg.mL⁻¹ dissolved in PBS was slowly added dropwise into the polymer organic solutions (first hour: 25 µL every 3 mins up to a final volume of 500 µL; second hour: 50 µL every 3 mins up to a final volume of 1500 µL, third hour: 50 µL every 3 mins up to a final added RhB solution equal to 2000 µL, then 50 µL of pure PBS every 3 mins up to a final added volume equal to 2500 µL, and finally 500 µL of PBS at once). The solvent was further removed by evaporation overnight and the final volume of the samples was set to 4.0 mL, therefore a polymer concentration of 4.0 mg.mL⁻¹. The samples were then purified by G50 column chromatography in PBS.

Characterization of the RhB-Loaded Vesicles

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS): Particle size measurements were conducted using an ALV/CGS-3 platform-based goniometer system (ALV GmbH). The

autocorrelation functions were collected using the ALV Correlator Control software. The counting time was 120 s and the distributions of sizes were obtained *via* the straightforward CONTIN analysis with hydrodynamic radii (R_H) calculated using the Stokes-Einstein relation with $D = \tau^{-1}q^{-2}$:

$$R_H = \frac{k_B T q^2}{6\pi\eta} \tau \quad (1)$$

k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, q is the scattering vector, η is the viscosity of the solvent and τ is the mean relaxation time related to the diffusion of the nanoparticles. The autocorrelation functions monitored at 90° were also analyzed using the Cumulant method.³⁶

$$\ln g_1(t) = \ln C - \Gamma t + \frac{\mu_2}{2} t^2 \dots \quad (2)$$

where C is the amplitude of the autocorrelation function, Γ is the relaxation frequency (τ^{-1}) and the parameter μ_2 is known as the second-order cumulant. This approach allowed for the determination of polydispersity indexes ($\text{PDI} = \mu_2/\Gamma^2$).

Static Light Scattering (SLS): The SLS measurements were carried out varying the scattering angle (θ) from 30° to 150° with a 15° stepwise increase. The molecular weight of the vesicles ($M_{w(\text{vesicles})}$) and the radius of gyration (R_G) of the assemblies were determined using the partial Berry approach as:

$$\left(\frac{Kc}{R_\theta} \right)^{1/2} = \left(\frac{1}{M_{w(\text{NPs})}} \right)^{1/2} \left[1 + \frac{R_G^2 q^2}{6} \right] \quad (3)$$

where the concentration c is given in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and K is the optical constant expressed by:

$$K = \frac{4\pi^2 n^2 \left(\frac{dn}{dc}\right)^2}{N_A \lambda^4} \quad (4)$$

R_θ (Rayleigh ratio) is the normalized scattered intensity (toluene was applied as standard solvent), n is the refractive index of the solvent, dn/dc is the refractive index increment determined on a classical Brice-Phoenix differential refractometer and N_A is the Avogadro's number. Therefore, measuring Kc/R_θ at a given angular range for one single concentration, the value of R_G is estimated from the slope of the curve and as $q \rightarrow 0$ the molecular weight ($M_{w(\text{vesicles})}$) is extracted from the inverse of the intercept.

Electrophoretic light scattering (ELS): Particle charge measurements were used to determine the average zeta potential (ζ) of the polymer colloids. The values were collected using a Zetasizer Nano-ZS ZEN3600 instrument (Malvern Instruments, UK) which measures the electrophoretic mobility (U_E) and converts the value to ζ -potential (mV) through Henry's equation:

$$U_E = \frac{2 \varepsilon \zeta f(ka)}{3 \eta} \quad (5)$$

where ε is the dielectric constant of the medium and η its viscosity. Furthermore, $f(ka)$ is the Henry's function calculated through the Smoluchowski approximation with $f(ka) = 1.5$.

Cryo-Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM): The cryo-TEM images were acquired on a FEI Tecnai G2 Spirit TWIN microscope using a bright-field imaging mode at accelerating voltage of 120 kV. Four- μ L of the samples were loaded into the electron microscopy grids covered with a holey or lacey carbon supporting film (Electron Microscopy Science) which were hydrophilized just before the experiment *via* glow discharge (Expanded Plasma Cleaner, Harrick Plasma, USA). The excess of the solution was removed by blotting (Whatman no. 1 filter paper), and the grids were plunged into liquid ethane held at -182 °C. The vitrified sample was then immediately transferred to the microscope and observed at -173 °C. The image analyses were performed using the ImageJ software.

Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS): SAXS profiles were acquired using a pinhole camera (MolMet, Rigaku, Japan, modified by SAXSLAB/Xenocs) attached to a microfocused X-ray beam generator (Rigaku MicroMax 003) operating at 50 kV and 0.6 mA (30 W). The samples were sealed into borosilicate capillaries (2 mm diameter) and the scattering intensities were recorded by using a Pilatus 300 K detector with an exposure time of 480 min. The isotropic 2D images were corrected by taking into account the detector dark noise and the data reduction were performed using a homemade software based on PyFAI Python library. The resulting $I(q)$ vs. q scattering curves were corrected by the subtraction of the scattering of the pure solvent. The fitting procedures were performed using the SASfit software.³⁷

Determination of RhB Loading Efficiency

The values of RhB loading efficiency were calculated as the ratio between the RhB amount determined in the polymersome formulations and the RhB feeding. One

hundred- μL of the purified samples was diluted with 400 μL of the acidic solution at $\text{pH} = 4.5$. Then, fluorescence spectroscopy measurements were carried out with excitation wavelength of 520 nm and emission spectra collected from 550 nm to 650 nm. The RhB contents were determined based on a RhB analytical curve with a linear response in the range 0.05-4.0 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ constructed using exactly the same environment conditions of pH and temperature (Supporting Information File - Figure S1).

Evaluation of the Permeability Behavior

The RhB elution profiles were evaluated by the dialysis method in PBS buffer at pH 6.9, 7.4, and 9.0. A pre-swollen cellulose dialysis membrane tube with MWCO 3.5 - 5.0 kDa (Spectra-Por[®] Float-A-Lyzer[®] G2) was filled with 6 mL of RhB-loaded vesicles 0.8 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. The membrane tube was then immersed into 1 L of the buffered solution at 37 °C under stirring (500 rpm). At pre-determined times, 100 μL of the RhB-loaded samples were taken from the membrane tubes and diluted with 400 μL of an acidic solution at $\text{pH} = 4.5$. The fluorescence spectroscopy measurements were then carried out with an excitation wavelength of 520 nm and emission spectra collected from 550 nm to 650 nm. The RhB contents were determined based on a RhB calibration curve constructed using exactly the same environmental conditions of pH and temperature (Supporting Information File - Figure S1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of the Block Copolymers

The block copolymers were synthesized by reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) polymerization. The hydrophilic polymer blocks PHPMA or PMeOx with a modified chain-transfer agent (CTA) were used as macro chain-transfer agent. The nonresponsive (PPPhA) and pH-responsive (PDPA) methacrylic monomers were then copolymerized in the presence of $\text{PHPMA}_m\text{-mCTA}$ or $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-mCTA}$, thus leading to nonresponsive and pH-responsive amphiphilic block copolymers. The molecular structures of the block copolymers used to prepare the RhB-loaded polymer vesicles are shown in Figure 1. The ^1H NMR spectra and SEC curves for $\text{PHPMA}_m\text{-mCTA}$, $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-mCTA}$ and respective block copolymers are given in the Supporting Information File (Figure S2-S6).

Figure 1. Molecular structure of $\text{PHPMA}_m\text{-}b\text{-PPPhA}_n$ (A) $\text{PHPMA}_m\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_n$ (B) and $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_n$ (C) block copolymers.

Since polymersomes were intended to be produced, the polymer chains were synthesized with higher amounts of the hydrophobic segments (PPPhA or PDPA) which would therefore permit the hydrophilic RhB encapsulation in the aqueous lumen. The Table 1 reports relevant characteristics of the polymer chains as determined by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR).

Table 1. Molecular characteristics of the block copolymers used in this investigation as determined by SEC and ^1H NMR.

Entry	M_n (SEC) ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	D	M_n (^1H NMR) ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	$M_n(\text{hydrophobic})$ ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) ^b	$w_{\text{hydrophilic}}$ ^e
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₃₅	7 770 ^a	1.20 ^a	10 200 ^c	7 700 ^c	0.24
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₅₅	11 870 ^a	1.14 ^a	14 400 ^c	11 900 ^c	0.17
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	17 560 ^a	1.17 ^a	30 800 ^c	26 200 ^c	0.15
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	28 250 ^a	1.26 ^a	52 000 ^c	45 300 ^c	0.13
PHPMA ₂₉ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₇₄	20 150 ^b	1.04 ^b	20 900 ^c	14 200 ^c	0.29
PHPMA ₂₅ - <i>b</i> -PPPhA ₁₈	18 500 ^b	1.10 ^b	16 860 ^d	9 675 ^d	0.19

^aDetermined by SEC in chloroform-triethylamine-isopropanol (94/4/2 v/v) using poly(methyl methacrylate) as the standard. ^bDetermined by SEC in DMF using poly(methyl methacrylate) as the standard. ^cDetermined by ^1H NMR in $\text{D}_2\text{O}/\text{DCl}$. ^dDetermined by ^1H NMR in DMF. ^eWeight fraction of the hydrophilic block based on ^1H NMR data.

Structural Characterization of the Assemblies

The RhB-loaded polymer vesicles and liposomes were prepared based on previously reported methodologies as earlier described. The structural characterization of the self-assemblies was performed using a combination of scattering and imaging, namely dynamic (DLS), static (SLS) and electrophoretic (ELS) light scattering, small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and cryo-transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM). The Figure 2 provides representative examples of acquired autocorrelation functions (A) with respective distributions of sizes (B) along with static light scattering data (C). The Table

2 compiles the structural features of the whole set of manufactured block copolymer self-assemblies as determined by light scattering measurements.

Figure 2. Representative light scattering data acquired for manufactured polymersomes according to the legend: (A) autocorrelation functions, (B) respective distributions of sizes and (C) static light scattering ($Kc/R_0^{1/2}$ vs. q^2) data with corresponding linear fittings ($c_{\text{polymer}} = 1.0 \text{ mg.mL}^{-1}$ in PBS pH 7.4).

Table 2. Structural features of the manufactured block copolymer self-assemblies as determined by light scattering measurements.

Entry	R_H (nm)	PDI	R_G/R_H	N_{agg}	ζ (mV)
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₃₅	85.2	0.06	1.02	11598	- 4.0
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₅₅	48.8	0.10	1.02	3217	- 1.6
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	33.8	0.06	0.96	913	-2.6
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	30.1	0.08	1.13	686	- 3.8
PHPMA ₂₉ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₇₄	34.0	0.17	1.17	663	- 7.0
PHPMA ₂₅ - <i>b</i> -PPPhA ₁₈	50.6	0.13	1.08	1584	- 13.5
Liposomes	58.2	0.13	1.11	n/a	- 2.5

The dynamic light scattering data (A-B) evidence the presence of distinct populations of nanoparticles. This feature has been consistently observed regardless of the chemical nature of the block copolymer. The values of molecular weight ($M_{w(vesicles)}$) and R_G were determined respectively from intercepts and slopes of profiles representatively reported in Figure 2C. The values of $M_{w(vesicles)}$ were used to calculate the aggregation numbers ($N_{agg} = M_{w(vesicles)}/M_{w(unimers)}$) whereas the values of R_G were used to compute structure-sensitive parameters ($\rho = R_G/R_H$) in order to probe the produced morphologies.

The experimental data suggest that the size of the polymersomes is influenced at least to some extent by the overall molecular weight of the block copolymer, or by the molecular weight of the hydrophobic block. Interestingly, the experimental data underline that the size is reduced when $w_{hydrophilic}$ is reduced. This is clearly shown for polymer vesicles produced from PMeO_{xm}-*b*-PDPA_n since smaller assemblies were developed

using PMeOx₅₁-based chains. Furthermore, the size of polymersomes produced from copolymers with similar hydrophilic-to-hydrophobic weight ratio (Table 1) is influenced by the molar mass of the hydrophobic block, which is accordingly a key factor governing the self-assembly phenomenon. Overall, longer polymer chains seem to conduct to smaller assemblies. Accordingly, an appropriate selection of molecular parameters is essential to generate assemblies with desired characteristics. The self-assembly behavior is driven by the curvature of the membrane and by the water solubility of the polymer chains.^{38,39} Low values of $w_{\text{hydrophilic}}$ in principle would induce the presence of low curvatures. Respectively, higher values of $w_{\text{hydrophilic}}$ are expected to induce the presence of high curvatures, accordingly conducting to the formation of smaller assemblies. Nevertheless, this trend is not observed in the series of produced self-assemblies as point out by the sizes reported in Table 2. Therefore, possibly the hydrated nature of the PDPA blocks (discussed hereafter) influences its flexibility and fluidity, which at least to some extent influence the vesicle formation. The size of the polymer vesicles truly reflects mainly the determined values of N_{agg} since higher values conduct to larger assemblies. The higher curvatures are accordingly linked to smaller sizes and N_{agg} .

Despite the different sizes, the formation of polymer vesicles is suggested by the ρ -parameter defined as R_G/R_H . The average radius of gyration (R_G) and hydrodynamic radius (R_H) were respectively measured in static and dynamic light scattering modes. This ratio is indicative of special morphologies or different architectures. Practically speaking, the ρ -parameter is equal to 0.774 for homogeneous (hard) spheres and it becomes larger for less compact and more anisometric particles.^{40,41} Polymersomes are self-assemblies filled and surrounded by the solvent therefore, the membrane (which contributes to R_G) is located at the surface of the vesicles. Since the scattering mass is concentrated on the surface of a sphere with radius R , and the hydrodynamic radius of a sphere is by definition

equal to the outer radius R , then $R_G/R_H = 1$ for hollow spheres.⁴² The determined values reported in Table 2 ($\rho \sim 1.0$) accordingly suggest the presence of polymer vesicles. The self-assembly of the copolymers into vesicles is even more robustly confirmed by the cryo-TEM images portrayed in Figure 3. The images indeed undoubtedly highlight the vesicular morphology of the produced self-assemblies.

Figure 3. Cryo-TEM images of self-assemblies produced from liposomes (A), PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₃₅ (B), PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈ (C) and PHPMA₂₉-*b*-PDPA₇₄ (D). The scale bars represent 100 nm.

The structural characterization of the polymer vesicles has been complementary performed by using the resources of SAXS, which is indeed a powerful technique to investigate membrane features. Representative SAXS profiles along with curve fittings for different manufactured assemblies are provide in Figure 4.

Figure 4. SAXS profiles (symbols) and respective curve fittings (solid lines) for the produced polymer vesicles prepared using PMeOX₅₁-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃, PHPMA₂₉-*b*-PDPA₇₄ and PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈ according to the legend.

The presence of polymersomes is suggested by the upward profiles at the low- q range following a q^{-2} power law dependence of the X-ray scattering intensity. Therefore, the oscillations located at $q \sim 0.2\text{-}1.0 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ is associated to the characteristics of the membranes. Accordingly, the scattering patterns could be adjusted by using a bilayered vesicle form factor. The adjustable parameters included the radius of the inner compartment consisting of water (R_c), the thickness of the hydrophilic outer section in contact with the solvent (t_h), the thickness of hydrophobic inner segment (t_i) and the respective electron densities of the solvent (η_{sol}), outer (η_h) and inner (η_i) sections of the bilayer. The electron density of water ($333 \text{ e}^-/\text{nm}^3$) was kept fixed during the fitting procedures. The SAXS profiles for the other PMeOX_{*m*}-*b*-PDPA_{*n*} block copolymer vesicles

were evidenced to be similar to the one reported in Figure 4, and the whole set of output parameters are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Structural parameters of the polymer vesicles as determined by SAXS (experimental dimensions are given in nm).

Entry	R_c	t_t	b_{exp}^a	t_h	<i>wall thickness</i>^b	R_t
PMeOx ₂₆ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₃₅	59.0	7.5	0.85	4.4	16.3	75.3
PMeOx ₂₆ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₅₅	40.0	9.8	0.82	4.6	19.0	59.0
PMeOx ₅₁ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	37.0	13.4	0.76	7.8	29.0	66.0
PMeOx ₅₁ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	37.4	17.8	0.73	7.0	31.8	69.2
PHPMA ₂₉ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₇₄	44.1	10.7	0.78	4.5	19.7	63.8
PHPMA ₂₅ - <i>b</i> -PPPhA ₁₈	51.7	3.6	0.79	4.1	11.8	63.5

$${}^a b_{exp} \text{ for } t_t = a.N^b; {}^b \text{ wall thickness} = t_h + t_t + t_h; R_t = R_c + \text{wall thickness}$$

The membrane of the PDPA-based polymer vesicles is thicker compared to the value determined for PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈. This is indeed visually suggested by the shoulder located at a higher and lower- q range respectively for PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈ and representatively for PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ in Figure 4. This to some extent reflects the degree of polymerization of the hydrophobic blocks. Additionally, theoretical predictions possibly suggest extended polymer chains inside de assemblies. The PDPA membrane thickness was estimated as $t_{PDPA(theo)} = a.N^b$ where “ a ” is the length of a PDPA repeating unit, “ N ” is the degree of polymerization of the PDPA segment, and “ b ” is a scaling exponent related to the chain conformation. The value of $b = 1$ is assigned for fully stretched chains, whereas $b = 0.5$ is for Gaussian coils. The value of $b = 2/3$ is expected for entangled polymeric membranes. Taking into account the length of a PDPA repeating

unit (0.367 nm),⁴³ the membrane thickness of the PDPA-based vesicles considering $b = 2/3$ as a realistic value would be smaller than the experimental values reported in Table 3. We indeed list in Table 3 the values of “ b ” which would match the experimental dimensions. They range from 0.73 to 0.85 and accordingly, the SAXS data underscore that the PDPA chains adopt a relatively extended conformation (uncoiled chains) within the membranes. This behavior can be linked to a solvation phenomenon due to the solution pH lying close to $pK_{a(PDPA)}$ (~ 6.8) which results in approximately 20% of the amino groups in the PDPA chains still protonated at $pH = 7.4$ ³⁴ and presumably conducting to the formation of swollen hydrophobic membranes. Another explanation for such deviation is the possible presence of partially interdigitated chains within the membranes. Regardless of the actual scenario, this feature markedly influences the permeability behavior of PDPA-based polymersomes as described and discussed in the next section. According to the SAXS data and respective fitting approach, the PPPhA membrane is thinner and the chains also seem also to adopt an extended or interdigitated conformation inside the membrane. If one takes into account the typical step length of methacrylate-based repeating units, which are in the range of 0.45 nm⁴⁴ and $t_{PPPhA(theo)} = a \cdot N^b$, the PPPhA membrane thickness would be in the range of 3.1 nm for $b = 2/3$, therefore smaller than the value obtained *via* SAXS fitting (3.6 nm). Nevertheless, the more hydrophobic feature of such polymer block, and the possible presence of particular intermolecular forces conduct to notable different permeability behavior compared to the PDPA membranes as discussed in the following section.

Evaluation of the Permeability Behavior

The investigations concerning the permeability behavior of the polymersomes were initiated by evaluating the values of loading efficiency as reported in Table 4. The

determined values range from 3-16%. The values possibly reflect the volume of the aqueous lumen (R_c) as well as the number of particles per volume unit present in each sample. Since the polymer concentration was kept fixed during sample preparation (4.0 mg.mL⁻¹), but values of N_{agg} depends on the supramolecular system (Table 2), the number of particles per volume unit is accordingly different. For instance, the calculated number of particles per liter for PMeOX₂₆-*b*-PDPA₅₅ (5.2×10^{16}) is 2.6 times higher compared to PMeOX₂₆-*b*-PDPA₃₅ (2.0×10^{16}) which accordingly reflects the smaller value of N_{agg} for the first case. Additionally, rough estimations based on the values of R_H and N_{agg} resulted in volume (%) of the polymersomes in the samples within the range of 1-5%. Therefore, although there seems not to be a driven force governing RhB encapsulation, the protocol of preparation conducted a rather preferred partition of the probe in the aqueous lumen of the polymer vesicles.

Subsequently, the influence of the solution pH in the permeability profile has been investigated and the experimental data for PMeOX₅₁-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ are reported in Figure 5A. This figure portrays the values of cumulative release (%) as a function of time for RhB-loaded PMeOX₅₁-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ polymersomes at three different pH.

Figure 5. Release profiles of RhB-loaded vesicles as a function of time according to the legends.

The experimental data evidence that the release is initially faster and afterwards, it is progressively reduced, accordingly following a non-linear trend. The permeability of RhB as a function of time is clearly pH-dependent and the profiles could be adjusted by using an exponential growth as:

$$CR(t) = Ae^{(-t/\tau)} + CR_{max} \quad (6)$$

CR refers to the cumulative release as a function of time (t). The adjustable parameters CR_{max} , τ and A are assigned respectively to the maximum release, characteristic time, and an offset. The values of τ are linked to the kinetics of RhB release. Indeed, instead of fitting a single set of data using several different models, this approach provides plausible interpretations of the fitting parameters to understand the pH sensitive release response. The adjustable parameters with physical meaning (CR_{max} and τ) are all given in Table 4 for the whole set of investigated systems, and accordingly discussed.

The RhB-loaded polymer vesicles were firstly purified by G50 column to ensure the complete removal of the unencapsulated probe. The RhB permeability as a function of time was assessed by fluorescence spectroscopy. The profiles reported in Figure 5 indeed demonstrate the permeable feature of the PDPA membranes. Regardless of the solution pH, RhB elutes almost quantitatively after approximately 5 days, and with values of y_{max} always higher than 0.92 at the end of the experiments. The kinetics is nevertheless pH-dependent and the probe release is faster at the low pH (pH = 6.9).

The characteristic time is related to the diffusion of the probe towards the polymeric membranes. The quantitative data provided in Table 4 along with the resulting R-square values confirm that the experimental profiles can be fitted with the selected exponential function (R-square values always higher than 0.962 have been reached).

Table 4. Fitted parameters of permeability data as obtained by fitting the experimental profiles reported in Figure 5 using the Equation 6.

Entry	pH	τ (hs)	CR _{max}	R-square	LE (%)
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₃₅	6.9	19 ± 2	0.96 ± 0.02	0.984	11.2
	7.4	27 ± 3	0.94 ± 0.04	0.963	11.2
	9.0	35 ± 5	0.92 ± 0.02	0.985	11.2
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₅₅	7.4	30 ± 3	0.94 ± 0.01	0.994	16.7
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	7.4	27 ± 1	0.98 ± 0.01	0.998	8.7
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	6.9	4.6 ± 0.7	0.97 ± 0.01	0.996	5.8
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	7.4	24 ± 1	0.93 ± 0.03	0.981	5.8
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	9.0	28 ± 2	0.90 ± 0.03	0.976	5.8
PHPMA ₂₉ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₇₄	7.4	28 ± 2	0.88 ± 0.02	0.993	4.0
PHPMA ₂₅ - <i>b</i> -PPPhA ₁₈	7.4	24 ± 3	0.44 ± 0.02	0.981	14.2
Liposomes	7.4	4.5 ± 0.6	0.87 ± 0.03	0.978	4.0

The trends highlight remarkably faster probe diffusion at lower pH with the characteristic time roughly 5-6 times smaller at pH 6.9 compared to the basic conditions for PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ vesicles. This is presumably linked to the pH-responsiveness of the PDPA block. The pK_a(PDPA) is equal to 6.8 and, as the pH reduces, the molar ratio of protonated species becomes higher thus resulting in the presence of more swollen hydrophobic segments. Accordingly, the chains are expected to adopt more extended conformation and the swollen feature possibly enables faster RhB diffusion toward the outer compartment. The characteristic times at pH 7.4 and 9.0 are not remarkably different within experimental errors. Indeed, at pH 7.4 approximately 80% of the PDPA are already deprotonated conferring them a less degree of swelling. This value reaches

almost 100% at pH 9.0.³⁴ Therefore, this investigation confirms that the PDPA membranes are inherently permeable even when the amino groups are fully deprotonated i.e., at basic pH. The influence of the solution pH has been confirmed regardless of the diblock copolymer used to produce the polymer vesicles. Similar data are provided in Table 4 for PMeOx₂₆-*b*-PDPA₃₅ where the pH influence is clearly observed in the values of characteristic time (the release profiles are provided in the Supporting Information File - Figure S7).

We have subsequently investigated the influence of the chemical nature of the hydrophobic segment in the permeability behavior. The solution pH was therefore kept fixed in these investigations and the cumulative release (%) has been evaluated for RhB-loaded PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PDPA₇₄, PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈ along with the manufactured liposomes for comparison purposes. The experimental results reported in Figure 5B underline that the liposomes are highly permeable to RhB with a characteristic time of approximately 4.5 hs. The bilayer membranes in liposomes are relatively thin and readily deformable typically leading to inadequate barrier properties. Truly, the experimental data underscore that polymersomes are less permeable than liposomes which is, at least to some extent, linked to the thicker block copolymer membranes compared to lipidic counterparts. Indeed, due to differences in molecular weight, the bilayer thickness is about 3-5 nm for liposomes whereas the values are commonly in the range 5-50 nm for polymersomes. This feature possibly explains the leaky behavior and very poor RhB retention in liposomes. Indeed, the low molecular weight and high lateral fluidity of liposomes leads to greater permeability, respectively, the polymer vesicles retain the cargo to a higher extent. Nevertheless, the PDPA membranes are demonstrated to be also inherently permeable, although the reported values of characteristic time are notably higher than the one reported for liposomes (roughly 6-7 times higher). This characteristic

can be dependent on the overall molecular weight and the nature of the hydrophobic block. In this investigation, the intrinsic permeability is possibly due to the $pK_{a(PDPA)}$ lying close to the solution pH conferring to them a certain level of swelling. Although thinner compared to the PDPA membrane due to disparate degrees of polymerization, the PPPhA membranes confer to the polymer vesicles a much more robust barrier property. Possibly its more hydrophobic feature conduct to reduced mobility and flexibility, thus restricting probe diffusion towards the outer compartment. Furthermore, a distinct configuration of the PPPhA chains in the polymer membrane may influence the behavior. The PPPhA blocks may undergo to noncovalent π - π stacking interaction (orbital overlap) between the π bonds of the aromatic rings, thus restricting the chain mobility in comparison to PDPA membranes. Such possibility is supposed to result in stronger permeability barrier. The experimental data reported in Figure 5B and Table 4 underlines that only 44% of the RhB amount was released from PHPMA₂₅-*b*-PPPhA₁₈ vesicles at the end of the experiment, which thus confirm the barrier property promoted by the PPhA₁₈ segment. Overall, these experimental data point out that the hydrophobic character, polymer chain configuration and the nature of intermolecular interactions are possibly highly relevant to guide membrane permeability.

We have also investigated the influence of the chemical nature of the stabilizing hydrophilic shell in the permeability behavior. Accordingly, investigations were performed for polymersomes containing a PHPMA or a PMeOx shell, and the experimental data are reported in Figure 5C for PHPMA₂₉-*b*-PDPA₇₄ and PMeOx₂₆-*b*-PDPA₅₅ since these block copolymers hold a fairly similar degree of polymerization of the hydrophobic segment (PDPA). The experimental data demonstrate that the permeability seems to be independent of the hydrophilic shell and it is mainly governed by the PDPA membrane. The characteristic times are close to 30 hs, regardless of the

hydrophilic shell, and the values of CR_{max} are close 0.90 once again confirming the permeable nature of the PDPA membranes. The shell-independent behavior has been further confirmed by the cumulative release profile for RhB-loaded $PMeO_{x51}-b-PDPA_{83}$ vesicles which also has a fairly similar PDPA degree of polymerization (Figure S8 - Supporting Information File). The similar value of the fitted parameters ($CR_{max} = 0.97 \pm 0.01$ and $\tau = 29 \pm 2$ hs) confirm that indeed, the chemical nature of the stabilizing hydrophilic shell seems not to be involved in the permeability features.

In the step further, $PMeO_{xm}-b-PDPA_n$ block copolymers having PDPA blocks with different degrees of polymerization have been further selected in order to investigate the influence of the membrane thickness in the permeability profile. The experimental data indeed underline that the membrane thickness does not remarkably influence the permeability behavior. The cumulative release (%) for RhB-loaded $PMeO_{x51}-b-PDPA_{113}$, $PMeO_{x51}-b-PDPA_{210}$, $PMeO_{x26}-b-PDPA_{35}$ and $PMeO_{x26}-b-PDPA_{55}$ polymersomes are provided in Figure 5D. These data decently compare the permeability behavior as a function of the thickness of the hydrophobic membrane respectively, the degree of polymerization of the PDPA block. The experimental results highlight that, even varying substantially the degree of polymerization of the PDPA block, it was not noticed a relevant or consistent trend in the permeability profile. Accordingly, the PDPA membrane seems to overall allow for the RhB diffusion at a similar time scale. This experimental results to some extent diverge compared to those reported previously by Xu et al.⁴⁵ Nevertheless, in the referenced investigation the hydrophobic membranes include poly[2-(diisopropylamino)ethyl methacrylate] (PDPA) and poly(benzyl methacrylate) (PBzMA), and the release behavior has been investigated at $pH = 4.0$ where PDPA chains are fully protonated. The release profile accordingly depends on the disaggregation of the vesicles when high PDPA contents are present, and sustained RhB release was achieved

only when high amounts of PBzMA were present, thus imparting much poorer membrane permeability. Hence, although frequently the high molecular weight constituents of the polymersome increase the microstructural stability of the self-assemblies, but also the barrier against diffusion, we herein underscore that this seems not to be always the case. Indeed, the hydrophobic PDPA membranes are relatively thick compared to PPPh₁₈ (Table 3) nevertheless, they confer a much higher degree of permeability. Accordingly, the permeable nature of the PDPA-based vesicles seems to be mostly linked to the chemical features of the polymer chains and their degree of packing within the membranes.

CONCLUSIONS

Following early investigations reported by us concerning the self-assembly of PDPA-based block copolymers into polymer vesicles,^{34,46} we herein demonstrate that PDPA membranes are inherently permeable to small molecules. The PDPA membranes are supposed to be relatively water-swollen and therefore, the membrane thickness has a minor influence in the behavior. Similarly, the chemical nature of the stabilizing shell plays a minor role in the elution profiles. Although the cumulative release follows an exponential growth, the kinetics of permeability depend on the chemical nature of the membrane, and it can still be modulated by the solution pH for the pH-responsive assemblies. Besides, the RhB permeability in liposomes is notably faster compared to polymersomes as most probably linked to the chemical and structural features of the hydrophobic segments. Truly, the biological applications of polymersomes have been limited by lack of permeability,^{22,47} and these findings constitute a step forward in the field towards finding intrinsically permeable polymer membranes which would then avoid tedious and time-consuming multistep post-synthetic procedures to produce pores for imparting vesicle permeability. Although other building blocks can also impart

intrinsic permeability to polymer vesicles,^{25,27} due to $\text{pK}_{\text{a}}(\text{PDPA}) = 6.8$ lying close to the physiological pH (7.4), the PDPA membranes can still sense minimal changes in the environmental conditions, enabling to some extent the modulation of the permeability in a biologically relevant pH window. These findings, fundamental in nature, possibly apply for a variety of hydrophilic small molecules if the localization inside the aqueous lumen of polymersomes is insured with great certainty. In this regard, we have further investigations underway aiming to correlate the *in vivo* performance of a variety of drug-loaded stimuli-responsive polymersomes with permeability profiles of a hydrophilic therapeutic drug (doxorubicin hydrochloride). The possibility to regulate flow of chemicals close to the physiological pH is expected to allow the use of PDPA-based polymersomes in a wide array of disparate bio-related applications.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

RhB calibration curve used to determine the reported values of RhB loading efficiency and cumulative release; cumulative release profiles at different pH for RhB-loaded vesicles produced from $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_n$; ^1H NMR spectra and GPC traces for $\text{PHPMA}_m\text{-mCTA}$, $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-mCTA}$ and a series of diblock copolymers used in the investigation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge the sponsor by FAPESP (grants 2019/06634-8 and 2021/12071-6) and GAČR (grant 20-15479J). F.C.G. acknowledges the fellowship granted by CNPq (grant 303268/2020-4). F.A.O acknowledges the fellowships granted by FAPESP (grant 2019/12944-0). A.J. and E.J. acknowledge the financial support from the Czech Science Foundation (grant no. 20-13946Y for A.J and grant no. 20-15077Y for E.J.). This project has also received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and

innovation programme under the H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (grant 823883). The CEM at UFABC is acknowledged for providing accessibility to the Malvern light scattering apparatus.

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